

PHAROS

THE GREEK AI FACTORY

Training Needs in HPC, AI, and Privacy
Preservation in Greece
2025-2026 Report

Version: 0.1

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1. Introduction

In order to systematically identify and address skill gaps within the user community, a Training Needs Assessment Questionnaire has been developed. This initiative supports the project's strategic objectives and aligns with the broader High-Performance Computing (HPC) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) ecosystems. The primary goal was to establish a targeted and evidence-based training strategy, including the development of relevant course content and educational materials covering areas such as access to computational resources, development support services, AI registry usage, data management, and business-oriented innovation.

The questionnaire was mainly focused towards assessing a) the level of familiarity of stakeholders with Artificial Intelligence (AI), High-Performance Computing (HPC), and Privacy Preservation in AI and b) the level of interest in participating in training activities related to these domains.

In order to capture these needs, we have developed a training mapping framework based in EuroCC@Greece work (Figure 1) that depicts in the horizontal axis, the different types of HPC and AI Users and their associated skill level, classified into 5 key categories:

- **Level 1:** Informational (pre-HPC/AI) type of HPC/AI user - Introductory skill level
- **Level 2:** HPC/AI User (application user) - Beginner skill level
- **Level 3:** HPC/AI Developer (application developer) - Intermediate skill level
- **Level 4:** HPC/AI Expert type of user and HPC Administrator type of user - Advanced skill level
- **Level 5:** HPC/AI Trainer - Highly Advanced skill level

In the vertical axis, the types of learner stakeholder segments are divided into 3 categories:

- **Academia/Research:** including both students and the researchers (PhD and post-doctoral researchers, professors).
- **Industry:** (a) Industrial Researcher: Data Scientists and research software engineers from industrial communities (research positions only) and (b) Other non-research industrial positions in small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs) and large companies.
- **Public Sector:** including all public sector organizations.

This framework has facilitated both the creation of the survey and will also enable us to depict our study findings in order to understand the HPC/AI training needs of the Greek users ("demand" side of the HPC/AI training).

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Figure 1 HPC and AI training mapping framework [1]

The questionnaire has been distributed to start-ups, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), academic and research institutions, the public sector as well as other interested stakeholders and in the following sections we present the obtained results within the period starting from 29/7/2025 until 28/02/2026.

The questionnaire results indicate a highly diverse respondent base of 233 individuals (Figure 2), with strong representation from academia and research, which accounts for roughly half of participants (49.8%), followed by the private sector at about one third (30%) and the public sector at around one fifth (20.2%), highlighting balanced interest across the innovation ecosystem.

Figure 2 Distribution of employment sectors among respondents (N = 233)

In terms of specialization, respondents span a wide range of roles (Figure 3), with the largest groups coming from the public sector (notably ministries and public law entities), PhD students, software developers, and academic researchers at different career stages, alongside meaningful participation from SMEs, large companies, startups, and postgraduate and undergraduate students. This diversity suggests that **AI and HPC training demand is both cross-sectoral and cross-career**, requiring a layered training approach that addresses advanced

¹ S. Karozis, X. Ziouvelou, and V. Karkaletsis, "Mapping the national HPC ecosystem and training needs: The Greek paradigm," *Journal of Supercomputing*, vol. 79, pp. 10691–10705, 2023, doi: 10.1007/s11227-023-05080-y

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research and infrastructure needs, practical industrial AI and HPC skills, and foundational capacity building for students and early-career professionals.

Below the TNA analysis will be presented by target group, Academia, Private sector and Public sector, focusing on HPC, AI, Privacy and training preferences.

2. Academia

Within academia specifically (N=116), the distribution of main scientific disciplines closely mirrors the overall specialization profile, again dominated by Computer and Information Sciences, Engineering, Social and Natural Sciences (Figure 4). This suggests that academic respondents are already engaged in data- and computation-intensive research, but also that there is a substantial cohort from fields where HPC and AI adoption is emerging rather than mature. As a result, training activities must address heterogeneous backgrounds, balancing foundational concepts with domain-specific applications.

Figure 4 Percentage distribution of academic scientific disciplines

2.1 HPC

2.1.1 Overall HPC familiarity

Regarding the HPC familiarity, the survey indicates that while a majority of academic respondents have at least some familiarity with HPC, over 50% categorize themselves only at an introductory or basic level (Figure 5). Furthermore, a significant 20.7% report being not familiar with HPC at all, highlighting a substantial need for foundational training.

Figure 5 Distribution of HPC familiarity levels in academia

2.1.2 HPC familiarity by academic position

Analysis by academic position indicates that introductory and basic familiarity are the dominant levels across all ranks (Figure 6). Earlier-stage academics primarily report basic to intermediate HPC knowledge, whereas senior staff, such as postdoctoral researchers and professors, show a higher proportion of intermediate to highly advanced levels.

Figure 6 HPC familiarity across academic positions

2.1.3 HPC familiarity by scientific discipline

The following heatmap (Figure 7) reveals that Social Sciences have the highest concentration of users who are not familiar with HPC, suggesting a need for

specialized outreach in those fields. Agricultural Sciences report mainly introductory familiarity while the Natural Sciences, Humanities and Health Sciences, show higher concentration of basic knowledge of HPC. Conversely, Computer Science and Engineering hold the highest percentages of advanced and highly advanced users, indicating these fields have already established stronger computational research pipelines.

Figure 7 Heatmap of HPC familiarity across scientific disciplines

2.1.4 Current HPC usage

The data shows that nearly half of the respondents (48.3%) do not use HPC, which aligns with the high percentage of users reporting low familiarity (Figure 8). For those who do use it, the vast majority rely on existing software packages rather than developing their own tools, suggesting that training should focus on application usage rather than programming.

Figure 8 Distribution of HPC usage levels in academia

2.2 AI

2.2.1 Overall AI familiarity

In terms of AI familiarity, nearly half of academic respondents identify as basic AI users, while only a small minority reach advanced or highly advanced expertise (Figure 9). The distribution highlights a broad foundational awareness of AI but a relatively limited pool of high-level specialists.

Figure 9 Distribution of AI familiarity levels in academia

2.2.2 AI familiarity by academic position

Across most academic ranks, from undergraduate students to full professors, the majority report primarily basic familiarity with AI, though respondents are represented across intermediate to highly advanced levels as well (Figure 10). Postdoctoral researchers stand out as the exception, demonstrating greater overall experience, a higher proportion of advanced and highly advanced respondents, and fewer individuals at the more basic levels of familiarity.

Figure 10 AI familiarity across academic positions

2.2.3 AI familiarity by scientific discipline

AI familiarity varies substantially across disciplines, with Computer Science, Engineering, and Health Sciences showing the highest proportions of intermediate to advanced users (Figure 11). Humanities, Social Sciences and Agricultural Sciences remain concentrated at basic or introductory levels, indicating uneven AI integration across academic fields.

Figure 11 Heatmap of AI familiarity across scientific disciplines

2.2.4 Current AI usage

Most respondents from the academia sector rely on pre-built AI tools, with only a small proportion developing their own models or software (Figure 12). This indicates that while AI adoption is widespread in academia, hands-on development skills remain concentrated among a smaller subset of user-built AI tools, with only a small proportion developing their own models or software.

Figure 12 Distribution of AI usage levels in academia

2.3 Privacy preservation in AI

2.3.1 Experience and familiarity with privacy-preserving techniques

Based on a five-point familiarity scale (1 = “Not at all familiar”, 5 = “Very familiar”), most academic respondents report very low familiarity across all listed techniques, especially with more advanced methods such as homomorphic encryption, secure multiparty computation, and federated learning (Figure 13). Only data anonymization shows a more balanced distribution, highlighting it as the most commonly understood technique within academia.

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Figure 13 Familiarity with selected privacy-preserving techniques in ML/DL

A slight majority of respondents report having worked with sensitive or personal data, indicating that privacy considerations are relevant to a substantial portion of academic ML/DL work (Figure 14). However, a significant minority has not engaged with such data, reflecting diverse research contexts within academia.

Figure 14 Familiarity with projects involving sensitive or personal data

Most respondents have not implemented privacy-preserving techniques, despite many working with sensitive data (Figure 15). This gap suggests a need for targeted training and practical guidance to help researchers translate awareness into actual methodological adoption.

Figure 15 Application of privacy-preserving techniques in ML/DL projects

2.3.2 Perceived importance of privacy preservation

The majority of respondents consider privacy preserving methods moderately to very important for their work, with “very important” being the largest single category (Figure 16). This indicates strong perceived relevance, even though actual familiarity and implementation remain limited.

Figure 16 Importance of privacy preservation in current professional roles

2.3.3 Barriers to adoption

The most frequently reported barrier in applying privacy-preserving techniques is the lack of knowledge, indicating that academic users feel underprepared to apply privacy-preserving methods in practice (Figure 17). Limited tools and the perceived complexity of implementation also contribute significantly, suggesting that both training and accessible resources are needed to support adoption.

Figure 17 Adoption barriers for privacy-preserving methods

2.4 Training courses

2.4.1 Preferred learning methods

Online delivery is the most preferred format among academic respondents, indicating a strong inclination toward flexible and accessible training options (Figure 18). While blended formats also attract substantial interest, purely in-person events are favored by only a small minority.

Figure 18 Preferred training delivery formats in academia

Shorter training formats, especially sessions of 2-3 hours, are clearly preferred, suggesting that academics value concise, focused learning opportunities that fit easily into busy schedules (Figure 19). Longer, multiweek or monthly programs attract far less interest, indicating limited appetite for extended time commitments.

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Figure 19 Preferred course durations in academia

Respondents show strong agreement toward structured, guided learning formats such as on-demand video courses, expert-led webinars, and live hands-on workshops (Figure 20). Peer-support communities are also valued, though to a lesser extent, while alternative or unspecified methods receive mixed responses.

Figure 20 Preferred course types in academia

2.4.2 Interest levels across HPC/AI/Privacy - related topics

Interest across AI-related topics is strongest in (Figure 21) core technical domains such as machine learning, computer vision, and generative AI, where many academics report engagement at intermediate or advanced levels. In contrast, interdisciplinary themes, such as sustainability, language and culture, or certain AI/HPC applications, attract lower interest, suggesting they remain emerging or less integrated into current academic agendas. Meanwhile, topics related to responsible and secure AI, including ethics, cybersecurity, and privacy-preserving methods, show moderate but growing interest, indicating a gradual shift toward more holistic and governance-aware AI competencies.

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Figure 21 Interest levels across HPC/AI/Privacy - related courses in academia

2.5 Key points

The survey findings portray an academic community that is broadly aware of HPC, AI, and privacy-preserving technologies but remains significantly underprepared to use them effectively. The majority of respondents sit at introductory or basic proficiency levels across all three domains, with 20.7% reporting no HPC familiarity at all and nearly half (48.3%) not currently using HPC infrastructure. AI adoption follows a similar pattern, with most academics functioning as basic-level users of pre-built tools and only a small minority achieving intermediate to advanced capability. Privacy-preserving methods represent the most critical gap: respondents consistently report very low familiarity with these techniques despite a majority acknowledging their importance for research workflows involving sensitive or personal data.

A defining structural feature of the academic landscape is its pronounced disciplinary divide. Computer Science and Engineering demonstrate markedly higher technical competency across all three domains and represent potential nodes for internal knowledge exchange, while Social Sciences, Humanities, Agricultural Sciences, and Health Sciences remain concentrated at foundational levels. This heterogeneity signals that a single, undifferentiated training offering will be insufficient. Respondents' clear preference for online delivery, short-format sessions (2-3 hours), and structured learning modalities further reinforces the need for modular, flexible training that can integrate realistically into research schedules. With respect to interest in AI/HPC/Privacy courses, the data indicate that the strongest interest is concentrated at the Basic level, particularly in Computer Vision, Natural Language Processing & Large Language Models, and AI Ethics and Compliance. There is also notable demand in Sustainability – Environment & AI/HPC and Machine Learning, but the three most

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prominent domains overall are **Computer Vision, NLP/LLMs, and AI Ethics and Compliance.**

3. Private Sector

The private sector sample (**N=70**) shows a broad mix of company types (Figure 3b), with organisations classified as Other (27.1%), SMEs (25.7%), and Large companies (24.3%) forming the largest groups. Start-ups (21.4%) also represent a significant share, while Spin-offs (1.4%) account for only a very small proportion of participants.

With regards to the functional units' distribution (Figure 22), responses are predominantly from Other functions (52.8%), indicating that over half of participants come from units outside the core listed categories. Production (15.7%) and Sales (15.7%) follow, while Service (5.7%), Finance (4.3%), Marketing (2.9%), and HR (2.9%) represent smaller shares.

Among R&D respondents (N=11), the largest group are Researchers/Developers (36.4%), followed by Other roles (27.3%) (Figure 23). Research software engineers (18.2%) and Scientific programmers (18.2%) are equally represented, showing a balanced mix of research and technical development profiles.

Figure 22 Distribution of respondents by functional unit

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Figure 23 Distribution of respondents by R&D position

Furthermore, the scientific discipline of R&D respondents was assessed and results showed that Computer Science represents the largest share of private sector R&D employees (45.5%), followed by Engineering (27.3%) (Figure 24). Health Sciences account for 18.2%, while Natural Sciences have the smallest representation at 9.1%. Overall, the distribution highlights a strong concentration of technology- and engineering- focused expertise in private R&D.

Figure 24 Distribution of R&D respondents by scientific discipline

3.1 HPC

3.1.1 Overall HPC familiarity

HPC familiarity in the private sector is generally low, with most respondents either not familiar (28.6%) or having introductory knowledge (44.3%) of HPC (Figure 25). Only a small minority report basic or intermediate hands-on experience, and advanced expertise is almost absent. This highlights a clear capacity gap and limited practical engagement with HPC across private-sector organisations.

Figure 25 Distribution of HPC familiarity levels in the private sector

3.1.2 HPC familiarity by type of enterprise

As stated before, the private sector shows relatively low levels of HPC expertise, as most organizations, especially startups and SMEs, are clustered mainly at introductory levels (Figure 26). Larger companies show even higher rates of no exposure, while advanced expertise appears only in SMEs at a low percentage, underscoring a clear skills gap across the private sector.

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Figure 26 HPC familiarity across enterprise types

3.1.3 HPC familiarity by functional unit / R&D position

By functional unit:

The following heatmap (Figure 27) shows that HPC familiarity in the private sector is generally limited, with most departments concentrated in the “Not familiar” and “Intro” categories. Technical units such as R&D and Production demonstrate slightly broader familiarity, including some Basic and Intermediate levels, whereas HR and Marketing are almost exclusively at the lowest familiarity levels. Importantly, there are virtually no respondents at Advanced or Highly Advanced levels across departments, indicating a clear high-level skills gap within industry.

Figure 27 Heatmap of HPC familiarity across functional units

By R&D position:

Within R&D related roles, scientific programmers show the strongest practical engagement, concentrated at the basic level, while research software engineers span introductory to basic familiarity (Figure 28). Researchers and developers exhibit a wider distribution, including some intermediate level expertise, indicating that HPC use within R&D is present but still developing across different technical roles.

Figure 28 Heatmap of HPC familiarity across R&D scientific disciplines

3.1.4 Current HPC usage

A significant majority of private-sector respondents report that they do not use HPC at all, pointing to limited operational adoption (Figure 29). Around one-third rely on existing software packages, while only a very small proportion develop or use their own HPC software alongside existing tools. This suggests that HPC engagement in industry is primarily user-level and tool-driven rather than development-oriented.

Figure 29 Distribution of HPC usage levels in the private sector

3.2 AI

3.2.1 Overall AI familiarity

AI familiarity in the private sector is moderate, with most respondents positioned at the basic user level (54.4%) and only a small share reaching intermediate (17.1%), advanced (10%), or highly advanced (7.1%) expertise (Figure 30.). Introductory (7.1%) and non-familiar (4.3%) categories still represent a notable portion of the workforce, indicating that AI adoption is present but not yet deeply embedded across companies.

Figure 30 Distribution of AI familiarity levels in the private sector

3.2.2 AI familiarity by type of enterprise

Across enterprise types, AI familiarity varies widely across enterprise types, with both SMEs and startups showing broad distributions that span from introductory to highly advanced levels, indicating heterogeneous skill profiles within these groups (Figure 31). Large companies also display a spread of familiarity, though with fewer respondents at the highest expertise levels. Overall, no enterprise category demonstrates a strong concentration of highly advanced AI capability, suggesting that advanced AI skills remain limited across the private sector regardless of company type.

Figure 31 AI familiarity across enterprise types

3.2.3 AI familiarity by functional unit / R&D position

AI familiarity varies significantly across functional units, with business-oriented departments such as Finance, HR, and Sales showing mostly basic levels of AI knowledge (Figure 32). In contrast, Production, Marketing and R&D exhibit higher concentrations of basic to advanced familiarity. The “Other” category shows a widespread, indicating heterogeneous roles with varying degrees of AI exposure.

Figure 32 Heatmap of AI familiarity across functional units

Within R&D-related roles, scientific programmers show stronger engagement at introductory and intermediate levels, while researchers/developers span a broader range, including some highly advanced expertise (Figure 33). Research software engineers show a balanced distribution of AI familiarity, with similar proportions reporting intermediate and highly advanced expertise.

Figure 33 Heatmap of AI familiarity across R&D positions

3.2.4 Current AI usage

AI usage in the private sector is dominated by pre-built tools and platforms, which account for the clear majority of activity (Figure 34). A much smaller share of respondents develops their own AI models or combine custom and pre-built solutions, indicating that in-house AI development capacity is still limited. Only a very small fraction reports not using AI at all, suggesting that adoption is widespread even if most usage remains at a relatively accessible, tool-based level.

Figure 34 Distribution of AI usage levels in the private sector

3.3 Privacy preservation in ML/DL

3.3.1 Experience and familiarity with privacy-preserving techniques

Based on a five-point familiarity scale (1 = “Not at all familiar”, 5 = “Very familiar”), familiarity with privacy-preserving techniques is uneven, with private sector respondents most comfortable with widely used methods such as data anonymisation and privacy risk assessment (Figure 35). More advanced approaches, like homomorphic encryption and secure multiparty computation, show very low familiarity, highlighting a clear skills gap in specialised privacy-enhancing technologies.

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Figure 35 Familiarity with selected privacy-preserving techniques in ML/DL

Most respondents from the private sector (74.3%) report being familiar with projects that involve sensitive or personal data (Figure 36), indicating that such data handling is a routine part of their work.

Figure 36 Familiarity with projects involving sensitive or personal data

Only a small minority (17.1%) of respondents report applying privacy-preserving techniques in their ML/DL projects (Figure 37), indicating that practical adoption remains limited despite growing awareness. The overwhelming majority (82.9%) have not yet integrated such methods into their workflows, highlighting a clear gap between familiarity and real-world implementation.

Figure 37 Application of privacy-preserving techniques in ML/DL projects

3.3.2 Perceived importance of privacy preservation

Privacy preservation is viewed as highly relevant to most respondents' day-to-day work, with the majority rating it as moderately important (25.7%) and very important (24.3%) (Figure 38). Only a small minority consider it unimportant (10%), suggesting that awareness of privacy obligations is well established across roles.

Figure 38 Importance of privacy preservation in current professional roles

3.3.3 Barriers to adoption

The results point to a clear hierarchy in the barriers organisations face when trying to apply privacy-preserving techniques (Figure 39). **Lack of knowledge emerges as the dominant obstacle**, cited by a large share of respondents (38%), indicating a fundamental skills gap that limits adoption from the outset. Secondary barriers, such as insufficient tools or resources (20.4%) and the perceived complexity of implementation (21%), further reinforce the idea that organisations struggle both with expertise and with practical enablers. Management-related issues and miscellaneous concerns appear less frequently.

Figure 39 Adoption barriers for privacy-preserving methods

3.4 Training courses

3.4.1 Preferred learning methods

Online formats receive the highest preference (36.8%), followed by hybrid options (28.7%) that combine in-person and virtual participation (Figure 40). In-person only events attract noticeably fewer respondents (11.5%), with very few (2.3%) indicating uncertainty.

Figure 40 Preferred training delivery formats in the private sector

Short sessions of 2-3 hours are the most commonly preferred format (37.3%), with full-day and multi-day short sessions receiving similar levels of interest (17.8%) (Figure 41). Longer formats such as monthly or week-long sessions attract smaller but still visible portions of respondents.

Figure 41 Preferred course durations in the private sector

Across most resource types, respondents show strong agreement or strong interest, particularly for on-demand video courses, expert-led webinars, and hands-on workshops (Figure 42). Code-along tutorials and community forums also receive substantial support, though with a wider spread of neutral and disagreeing responses.

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Figure 42 Preferred course types in the private sector

3.4.2 Interest levels across HPC/AI/Privacy - related topics

Interest spans a wide range of AI-related topics, with strong engagement across core technical areas such as machine learning, computer vision, NLP, and Generative AI (Figure 43). Respondents also show notable interest in applied domains and governance-related themes, including Business Strategy and AI management, AI Ethics and Compliance, Cybersecurity for AI systems, sustainability, and privacy-preserving methods, across multiple proficiency levels.

Figure 43 Interest levels across HPC/AI/Privacy - related courses in the private sector

3.5 Key points

The private sector reveals a workforce that routinely handles sensitive data but lacks the technical foundation to do so in a privacy-preserving manner. HPC literacy is generally low, with 72.9% of respondents at either no familiarity

(28.6%) or introductory knowledge (44.3%), and virtually no advanced expertise observed across any company type or department. AI adoption is more widespread, with over half of respondents (54.4%) operating as basic-level users, though advanced skills remain limited and unevenly distributed. The most pressing finding is the privacy-implementation gap: despite 74.3% of respondents regularly working with sensitive data, 82.9% have not integrated privacy-preserving techniques into their ML/DL workflows, and the primary obstacle identified is the lack of knowledge (38%).

Company type and departmental role introduce meaningful variation in skill profiles. R&D and Production units show broader HPC and AI familiarity relative to administrative functions such as HR, Marketing, and Finance, while startups and SMEs demonstrate slightly more advanced AI engagement than larger companies. This functional stratification suggests that training interventions must be role-differentiated to be effective. Preferred delivery formats are short online or hybrid sessions which align well with the time-constrained realities of private-sector operations and should frame all program design. Analysis of interest levels in HPC/AI/Privacy training reveals that interest is skewed toward Advanced and Highly Advanced levels, with **Generative AI, Business Strategy & AI Management, AI Ethics and Compliance and Machine Learning** emerging as the top priorities. Natural Language Processing & Large Language Models and Cybersecurity for AI systems also show strong demand, but Generative AI and strategy-oriented AI topics dominate.

4. Public Sector

Considering the public sector composition (N=47), the majority of respondents (66%) come from the Narrow public sector, which includes ministries and public law entities, while the remaining 34% are drawn from the Wider public sector (Figure 3c).

4.1 HPC

4.1.1 Overall HPC familiarity

Overall familiarity with HPC is concentrated at the lower end of the spectrum, with most respondents reporting no experience (29.8%), introductory exposure (31.9%), or basic user-level knowledge (27.7%) (Figure 44). Only a small proportion indicate intermediate (8.5%) or advanced expertise (2.1%), showing that higher level HPC skills are much less common in the group.

Figure 44 Distribution of HPC familiarity levels in the public sector

4.1.2 HPC familiarity by public sector type

The Narrow public sector shows its highest concentrations at the introductory (42%) and basic (26%) familiarity levels, with very few respondents (9.7%) reporting intermediate knowledge (Figure 45). The Wider public sector shows its highest share at the non-familiar level (44%) followed by the basic (31%) and introductory (12%) familiarity levels.

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Figure 45 HPC familiarity across public sector types

4.1.3 Current HPC usage

Most respondents (59.6%) report not using HPC, while a notable share (36.2%) rely on existing software packages when they do engage with it (Figure 46). Only very small groups develop their own HPC software (2.1%) or combine custom and existing tools (2.1%).

Figure 46 Distribution of HPC usage levels in the public sector

4.2 AI

4.2.1 Overall AI familiarity

Most respondents (72.4%) place themselves at the basic level of AI familiarity while smaller groups report introductory (10.6%) or intermediate (10.6%) experience, and only a few (6.4%) identify themselves as advanced users (Figure 47).

Figure 47 Distribution of AI familiarity levels in the public sector

4.2.2 AI familiarity by public sector type

The heatmap (Figure 48) shows that both public sector groups cluster heavily (>70%) at the basic familiarity level, with the Narrow and Wider sectors each showing their highest values there. Introductory knowledge appears in smaller proportions, while intermediate and advanced familiarity are present only in limited pockets, with no respondents reporting highly advanced expertise.

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Figure 48 AI familiarity across public sector types

4.2.3 Current AI usage

Current AI usage in the public sector is dominated by pre-built tools, with 87.2% of respondents relying on ready-made AI platforms (Figure 49). Smaller groups report using both pre-built and custom software (6.4%), not using AI at all (4.3%), or developing their own AI models (2.1%).

Figure 49 Distribution of AI usage levels in the public sector

4.3 Privacy preservation in ML/DL

4.3.1 Experience and familiarity with privacy-preserving techniques

Based on a five-point familiarity scale (1 = “Not at all familiar”, 5 = “Very familiar”), the distributions in the bar plots (Figure 50) show that every privacy-preserving technique is concentrated at the lowest familiarity level, with only modest variation in how much familiarity increases beyond that baseline. Data anonymization is the only technique that shows a more “canonical” progression, with noticeable shares across the higher familiarity levels. For the other techniques, the distributions are more skewed and compressed: they still peak in the lowest familiarity category, but the rise into intermediate and advanced levels is much weaker and more fragmented.

Figure 50 Familiarity with selected privacy-preserving techniques in ML/DL

A clear majority of respondents (68.1%) report having experience with projects involving sensitive or personal data, indicating substantial exposure to data-intensive work (Figure 51). The remaining 31.9% have not worked with such projects, suggesting a meaningful but smaller group without direct hands-on familiarity.

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Figure 51 Familiarity with projects involving sensitive or personal data

A very small share of respondents (14.9%) report applying privacy-preserving techniques in their ML/DL projects, indicating that practical adoption remains limited (Figure 52). The overwhelming majority (85.1%) have not yet incorporated such methods, highlighting a significant gap between awareness and real-world implementation.

Figure 52 Application of privacy-preserving techniques in ML/DL projects

4.3.2 Perceived importance of privacy preservation

Most respondents from the public sector view privacy preservation as an important aspect of their current job, with the largest shares rating it as either moderately (29.8%) or very important (29.8%) (Figure 53). Only a small minority (8.5%) consider it unimportant, underscoring that privacy concerns are broadly recognised as a meaningful part of day-to-day responsibilities.

Figure 53 Importance of privacy preservation in current professional roles

4.3.3 Barriers to adoption

The most prominent barriers in applying privacy-preserving techniques in the public sector relate to capability gaps, with many respondents pointing to limited knowledge (31.3%) and insufficient tools or resources (27.7%) as the main obstacles (Figure 54). Practical challenges such as implementation complexity (22.9%) and organisational support (15.7%) appear less widespread but still meaningful.

Figure 54 Adoption barriers for privacy-preserving methods

4.4 Training courses

4.4.1 Preferred learning methods

Respondents show a clear preference for flexible formats, with blended in-person and online delivery emerging as the most appealing option (35.2%) (Figure 55). Fully online events also attract strong interest (31.5%), while purely in-person formats draw comparatively little enthusiasm (5.6%).

Figure 55 Preferred training delivery formats in the public sector

Short, focused sessions are the most preferred format, particularly those lasting just a few hours (31.4%) (Figure 56). Interest declines as duration increases, with short sessions ranking second (22.9%), while full-day events account for a comparable share (21.4%).

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Figure 56 Preferred course durations in the public sector

Interactive and structured learning formats, such as webinars, hands-on workshops, and on-demand video courses, receive the strongest positive sentiment (Figure 57). Community-based and code-along resources are also appreciated, though with more mixed views, while the “Other” category stands out for its fragmented and often negative responses.

Figure 57 Preferred course types in the public sector

4.4.2 Interest levels across HPC/AI/Privacy - related topics

The heatmap (Figure 58) shows broad interest across all AI-related topics, with substantial concentrations at both basic and intermediate levels. Applied domains such as machine learning, cybersecurity for AI, Business strategy, Generative AI, and computer vision attract the strongest intermediate engagement, while more specialised areas, like privacy-preserving methods, risk assessment, and high-performance computing, also show meaningful mid-level interest, though with a flatter profile. At the highly advanced end, responses are sparse across the board, with highest percentages in Machine Learning,

Generative AI, AI Ethics and Risk Assessment suggesting that advanced learning is also of high interest in the public sector.

Figure 58 Interest levels across HPC/AI/Privacy - related courses in the public sector

4.5 Key points

The public sector presents the most uniformly foundational skill profile across all three domains, combined with among the highest rates of real-world exposure to sensitive data-creating a particularly urgent training imperative. Nearly 90% of respondents sit at introductory level or below in HPC, and 59.6% do not use HPC at all. AI usage is almost exclusively reliant on pre-built tools (87.2%), with 72.4% of respondents self-assessing at the basic level. Privacy-preserving techniques are virtually absent from practice: only 14.9% report applying such methods, despite 68.1% having worked with sensitive or personal data, and the dominant barriers are limited knowledge (31.3%) and insufficient tools or resources (27.7%).

The structural split between the Narrow and Wider public sectors adds a further layer of complexity. While Narrow sector respondents cluster at introductory and basic familiarity, Wider sector entities show higher rates of non-familiarity across all three domains, indicating that more ground-up capacity building is required in the latter. Despite these gaps, public sector respondents express meaningful interest in advancing their knowledge, particularly in applied AI domains including machine learning, cybersecurity, generative AI, and privacy-preserving methods. The strong preference for blended and fully online delivery, alongside interactive formats such as webinars and hands-on workshops, provides a workable baseline for programme design. The highest interest for AI/HPC/Privacy courses, appears at the Intermediate level, especially in **Cybersecurity for AI Systems, Business Strategy & AI Management, and Generative AI**. Additionally, Computer Vision, AI Ethics and Compliance and Machine Learning

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attract considerable attention, but cybersecurity and governance-oriented AI themes are most prominent overall.

5. Conclusions

Across all three target groups, academia, private sector, and public sector, the Training Needs Assessment reveals a consistent and systemic pattern: widespread foundational skill levels in HPC, AI, and privacy-preserving techniques coexist with high exposure to sensitive data and a strong recognition of privacy's professional importance. The majority of respondents in every sector operate at basic or introductory levels in HPC and AI, and virtually all groups report critically low familiarity with advanced privacy-enhancing technologies. The primary barrier to adoption is lack of knowledge, not motivation. Respondents consistently rate privacy preservation as moderately to very important for their work, yet practical implementation lags far behind awareness across all sectors.

Disciplinary, organisational, and functional heterogeneity substantially shapes needs within each target group. In academia, Computer Science and Engineering communities stand apart as comparatively advanced, while Humanities, Social Sciences, and Agricultural Sciences require foundational pathways. In the private sector, R&D and Production units are better positioned than administrative functions. In the public sector, Wider sector entities require the most foundational support. Notably, training format preferences converge across all groups on online-first or blended, short-duration, structured delivery, providing a clear and consistent baseline for programme design.

The gap between data exposure and privacy-preserving capability constitutes the most urgent cross-cutting challenge identified in this assessment. A substantial share of respondents across all three sectors handles sensitive or personal data routinely, yet adoption of privacy-preserving methods in ML/DL workflows remains marginal everywhere. This points to a critical need for practical, hands-on training that bridges conceptual awareness and operational implementation, beginning with accessible methods such as data anonymisation and progressing toward federated learning and differential privacy. A coordinated, multi-tier training ecosystem spanning introductory to intermediate levels, adapted per target group and delivery context, is both justified and necessary.

6. Capitalize on TNA analysis: PHAROS Holistic Training Strategy

The Training Needs Assessment revealed a consistent pattern across all target groups:

- Widespread foundational skill levels in HPC (20-30% report no familiarity) and AI (50-72% at basic user level)
- Critically low familiarity with privacy-preserving techniques, particularly advanced methods such as homomorphic encryption and secure multiparty computation
- High exposure to sensitive or personal data (60-75% across sectors) combined with minimal practical adoption of privacy-preserving methods in ML/DL workflows (14-17%)
- Primary barrier to adoption: lack of knowledge (30-38%), not motivation
- Strong convergence on delivery format preferences: online-first or blended, short-duration (2-3 hours), structured and interactive

Based on the key points of TNA and the extended analysis, PHAROS has developed a training strategy according to the following principles:

1. **Progressive competency building:** Learners enter at their assessed tier and advance incrementally with clear learning outcomes linking each tier
2. **Context-specific customisation:** Content, case studies, and delivery modes are adapted to the disciplinary, organisational, and functional realities of each target group
3. **Online-first, hybrid-enabled:** Default delivery is online with hybrid options for intermediate and advanced tracks; in-person formats reserved for intensive Tier 3 programmes
4. **Modular and stackable:** Training units of 2-3 hours enable flexible participation and micro-credential accumulation
5. **Application-driven pedagogy:** Hands-on labs, code-along sessions, real-world scenarios, and se-case exercises prioritised over lecture-based formats
6. **Privacy-implementation focus:** Closing the gap between privacy awareness and operational deployment is the most urgent cross-cutting objective

6.1 Academia Training Strategy

6.1.1 Target Group Profile

Academic respondents demonstrate pronounced disciplinary heterogeneity. Computer Science and Engineering show markedly higher competency across HPC, AI, and privacy domains, while Social Sciences, Humanities, Agricultural Sciences, and Health Sciences remain concentrated at foundational levels. Nearly half (48.3%) do not currently use HPC, and privacy-preserving methods represent the most critical gap despite a majority acknowledging their importance.

Preferred delivery: Online (dominant), blended (substantial interest), 2-3 hour sessions, structured learning formats (on-demand video courses, expert-led webinars, live hands-on workshops).

6.1.2 Three-Tier Training Pathway

6.1.2.1. Tier 1 - Foundational Track

Target disciplines: Social Sciences, Humanities, Agricultural Sciences, Health Sciences

Domain	Content Focus	Format	Duration
HPC	What is HPC, when to use it, institutional access pathways, resource allocation basics	On-demand video modules + guided exercises	2-3 hrs/module
AI	Navigating pre-built AI tools, AI in research workflows, prompt design, responsible AI use	Expert-led webinar + self-paced follow-up	2-3 hrs
Privacy	GDPR in research, data anonymisation techniques, introduction to differential privacy, ethical data handling	Structured online course	2-3 hrs/module

Table 1 Academia Tier 1: Foundational Track

Learning outcomes:

1. Understand what HPC is and identify research scenarios where HPC is beneficial
2. Navigate institutional HPC access procedures and submit basic jobs
3. Use pre-built AI tools effectively and responsibly within research contexts

4. Apply GDPR-compliant data handling protocols and basic anonymisation techniques
5. Recognise when privacy-preserving methods are required in research projects

6.1.2.2. Tier 2 - Intermediate Track

Target disciplines: Natural Sciences, Engineering, Computer Science, Health Sciences (advancing users)

Domain	Content Focus	Format	Duration
HPC	Job submission and scheduling, parallel programming basics (OpenMP, MPI), domain-specific HPC use cases	Hands-on workshops (hybrid)	Half-day to full-day
AI	Model fine-tuning, transfer learning, ML frameworks in research (TensorFlow, PyTorch), experiment tracking	Live workshop + code-along sessions	Half-day
Privacy	Federated learning introduction, differential privacy in practice, secure data pipelines, privacy auditing basics	Expert-led webinar + lab exercises	Half-day

Table 2 Academia Tier 2: Intermediate Track

Learning outcomes:

1. Write and optimise parallel code for HPC systems using OpenMP and MPI
2. Fine-tune pretrained AI models for domain-specific research applications
3. Implement basic federated learning pipelines for multi-institutional collaboration
4. Apply differential privacy mechanisms to research datasets
5. Conduct privacy impact assessments for ML/DL research projects

6.1.2.3. Tier 3 - Advanced Track

Target audience: Computer Science/Engineering advanced cohorts, research software engineers, HPC facility staff

Domain	Content Focus	Format	Duration
HPC	GPU programming (CUDA, OpenACC), HPC-AI convergence, performance optimisation and profiling, containerisation for HPC	Multi-day bootcamp + project work	2-3 days
AI	Custom model development, MLOps for research, large-scale AI on HPC, distributed training strategies	Intensive bootcamp	2-3 days

Privacy	Homomorphic encryption, secure multiparty computation, privacy auditing of models, trusted execution environments	Intensive workshop	1-2 days
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Table 3 Academia Tier 3: Advanced Track

Learning outcomes:

1. Develop GPU-accelerated applications using CUDA and OpenACC
2. Deploy large-scale AI training pipelines on HPC infrastructure
3. Implement advanced privacy-enhancing technologies including homomorphic encryption and secure multiparty computation
4. Conduct privacy audits of ML models to detect and mitigate leakage
5. Lead privacy-preserving AI research projects and mentor junior researchers

6.2 Private Sector Training Strategy

6.2.1 Target Group Profile

The private sector workforce routinely handles sensitive data (74.3%) but demonstrates limited technical foundation in HPC (72.9% at no familiarity or introductory level) and predominantly basic-level AI usage (54.4%). The most pressing finding is the privacy-implementation gap: 82.9% have not integrated privacy-preserving techniques into ML/DL workflows despite high exposure to sensitive data, with lack of knowledge cited as the primary barrier (38%).

Company type and departmental role introduce meaningful variation: R&D and Production units show broader HPC and AI familiarity relative to administrative functions (HR, Marketing, Finance), while startups and SMEs demonstrate slightly more advanced AI engagement than larger companies.

Preferred delivery: Online (36.8%), hybrid (28.7%), short sessions (2-3 hours preferred at 37.3%).

6.2.2 Three-Tier Training Pathway

6.2.2.1. Tier 1 - Role-Based Awareness Track

Target roles: HR, Marketing, Finance, Sales, Administrative Functions

Domain	Content Focus	Format	Duration
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HPC	What HPC is and why it matters for business operations, cloud vs. HPC trade-offs	Short online awareness module	1-2 hrs
AI	Leveraging pre-built AI tools, interpreting AI outputs responsibly, AI literacy for non-technical roles	Online self-paced module + use cases	2-3 hrs
Privacy	GDPR compliance fundamentals, data handling protocols, privacy risk awareness, organisational obligations	Online course aligned with regulatory obligations	2-3 hrs

Table 4 Private Sector Tier 1: Role-Based Awareness Track

Learning outcomes:

- Understand when HPC or advanced compute resources are relevant to business processes
- Use pre-built AI tools competently and interpret outputs with appropriate critical awareness
- Apply GDPR-compliant data handling protocols in day-to-day operations
- Identify privacy risks and escalate appropriately within organisational governance structures

6.2.2.2. Tier 2 - Applied Technical Track

Target roles: R&D, Production, Technical Specialists, Scientific Programmers, Data Analysts

Domain	Content Focus	Format	Duration
HPC	Using HPC clusters, optimising compute workflows, HPC-cloud integration, containerisation (Docker, Singularity)	Hybrid hands-on lab	Half-day to full-day
AI	Applied ML for product development, computer vision, NLP in production, model deployment pipelines	Online workshop + hands-on exercises	Half-day
Privacy	Privacy-by-design in data pipelines, anonymisation tools, differential privacy deployment in production systems	Hybrid lab workshop	Half-day

Table 5 Private Sector Tier 2: Applied Technical Track

Learning outcomes:

- Submit and manage jobs on HPC infrastructure, optimising resource usage
- Deploy ML models in production environments with appropriate monitoring and versioning
- Implement privacy-by-design principles in data engineering pipelines
- Apply anonymisation techniques and differential privacy to production datasets
- Conduct privacy impact assessments for commercial AI/ML products

6.2.2.3. Tier 3 - Expert Track

Target roles: Data Scientists, Research Engineers, ML Engineers (especially in SMEs and Start-ups), Technical Leads

Domain	Content Focus	Format	Duration
HPC	Scaling AI workloads on HPC, parallel algorithm design, distributed computing frameworks (Dask, Ray)	In-person or partner-university bootcamp	2-3 days
AI	Custom model development, MLOps best practices, federated learning deployment, model interpretability and explainability	Intensive in-person workshop	2 days
Privacy	Federated learning in production, homomorphic encryption for secure computation, secure multiparty computation, privacy auditing of deployed models	Intensive in-person workshop	1-2 days

Table 6 Private Sector Tier 3: Expert Track

Learning outcomes:

- Architect and deploy large-scale AI training pipelines on HPC infrastructure
- Implement end-to-end MLOps workflows including CI/CD for ML, monitoring, and governance
- Deploy federated learning systems for privacy-preserving multi-party collaboration
- Implement homomorphic encryption and secure multiparty computation in production systems
- Lead privacy-preserving AI initiatives within organisations and mentor technical teams

6.3 Public Sector Training Strategy

6.3.1 Target Group Profile

The public sector presents the most uniformly foundational skill profile across all three domains, combined with among the highest rates of real-world exposure to sensitive data (68.1%), creating a particularly urgent training imperative. Nearly 90% of respondents sit at introductory level or below in HPC, 59.6% do not use HPC at all, and AI usage is almost exclusively reliant on pre-built tools (87.2%). Privacy-preserving techniques are virtually absent from practice: only 14.9% report applying such methods despite widespread sensitive data handling.

The structural split between Narrow public sector (ministries, public-law entities-66%) and Wider public sector (agencies, state enterprises-34%) adds

complexity. Wider sector entities show higher rates of non-familiarity across all domains, indicating more ground-up capacity building is required.

Preferred delivery: Blended in-person and online (35.2%), fully online (31.5%), interactive and structured learning formats (webinars, hands-on workshops, on-demand video courses).

6.3.2 Three-Tier Training Pathway

6.3.2.1. Tier 1 - Mandatory Awareness and Foundation Track

Target audience: All public sector staff, especially Wider public sector entities

Domain	Content Focus	Format	Duration
HPC	HPC and cloud computing for public services: use cases, national infrastructure overview, access mechanisms	Online module + facilitated Q&A session	2-3 hrs
AI	Understanding AI in the public sector: tools, ethics, policy context, AI Act implications, responsible AI deployment	Blended webinar + structured exercises	2-3 hrs
Privacy	Privacy by default in public services: GDPR obligations, sensitive data handling protocols, citizen data rights, NIS2 Directive basics	Mandatory online course	2-3 hrs

Table 7 Public Sector Tier 1: Mandatory Awareness and Foundation Track

Learning outcomes:

- Understand the role of HPC and cloud computing in modernising public services
- Navigate national HPC infrastructure access procedures relevant to public sector entities
- Recognise AI use cases in public administration and understand AI Act risk categories
- Apply GDPR-compliant data handling protocols specific to public sector obligations
- Identify when privacy impact assessments are required for public sector AI/ML projects

6.3.2.2. Tier 2 - Applied Professional Track

Target audience: Data analysts, IT staff, policy officers, digital transformation teams (Narrow public sector focus)

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Domain	Content Focus	Format	Duration
HPC	Job scheduling basics, data processing pipelines on HPC infrastructure, managing large-scale public datasets	Online lab + expert-led webinar	Half-day
AI	AI for public service optimisation, cybersecurity for AI systems, risk assessment methodologies, AI transparency and explainability	Webinar + hands-on exercises	Half-day
Privacy	Privacy impact assessments (PIA), anonymisation of public datasets, privacy-preserving analytics, secure data sharing across agencies	Hands-on workshop (hybrid)	Half-day

Table 8 Public Sector Tier 2: Applied Professional Track

Learning outcomes:

- Submit and manage data processing jobs on HPC systems for public sector use cases
- Deploy AI tools for public service optimisation with appropriate risk assessment and transparency mechanisms
- Conduct privacy impact assessments for public sector AI/ML systems
- Apply anonymisation techniques to public datasets for open data initiatives
- Implement privacy-preserving analytics in multi-agency data sharing contexts

6.3.2.3. Tier 3 - Advanced Leadership Track

Target audience: Digital officers, data science teams, IT leadership, senior analysts, policy directors

Domain	Content Focus	Format	Duration
HPC	HPC for large-scale government data processing, AI workloads on national HPC infrastructure, strategic planning for computational capacity	Multi-day workshop + collaboration with national HPC centres	2 days
AI	Generative AI governance frameworks, AI ethics frameworks for public sector, advanced risk and audit methodologies, algorithmic transparency	Multi-day intensive + policy simulation exercises	2 days
Privacy	Advanced privacy-preserving techniques deployment, auditing AI models for privacy leakage, regulatory alignment (GDPR, AI Act, NIS2), secure federated data ecosystems	Intensive workshop + EU-level peer exchange	1-2 days

Table 9 Public Sector Tier 3: Advanced Leadership Track

Learning outcomes:

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- Develop strategic plans for leveraging national HPC infrastructure for government data processing and AI initiatives
- Design and implement AI governance frameworks aligned with EU AI Act and national digital strategies
- Lead privacy-preserving AI initiatives across government agencies
- Conduct privacy audits of deployed AI systems and ensure regulatory compliance
- Establish secure federated data ecosystems for cross-agency collaboration while preserving citizen privacy